

Tourism Activities for Elderly's in Thailand

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ABSTRACT : This paper aimed to study 1) Tourism Activities for Elderly's in Thailand with the quantitative method, the questionnaire covered 400 samples of Thai Elderly Tourists with non-probability and accidental sampling. Then, the data were analyzed with descriptive statistics for the respondent's information and with the correlation and multiple regression to find out any concordances between the Tourism Activities and elderly's in Thailand. The research indicated that 1) for the whole of the need, activities (X_1) ($\beta = 0.512$, $\alpha < .01$) and time (X_4) ($\beta = 0.327$, $\alpha < .05$) had a statistically significant effect on the Elderly's in Thailand.

KEYWORDS - tourism; activities ;elderly's.

I. INTRODUCTION

Government policies related to tourism are important in driving tourism. There are many aspects of Thailand such as the development of quality tourism. Income distribution from Travel to the local The development of eco-friendly tourism And enhancing the image Of tourism in the eyes of tourists around the world he use of information technology in Promote tourism under the concept of "Thailand 4.0" and focus on tourism It is an industry with regard to security, economy, society, psychology and foreign affairs. Are integrated everywhere. Sector to aim to be a world-class tourist destination of water quality Is growing on the basis Of Thai And distribute income to the community [1] Causing the country to turn their attention and Give priority to quality tourism Including quality tourism management to accommodate tourists Quality too With the Association for the Promotion of Tourism Asia and the Pacific (PATA) said That quality tourism is tourism that conserves natural resources And tourists are interested Learning [2] tourism In addition, quality tourism is Tourism of Elderly traveler That does not focus on the rush Slow travel Focus on touch-based tourism. And learn to appreciate Therefore, the elderly tourists are a group Quality tourists that have become a tourist market that many countries focus on to attract Quality tourists to travel in their country As in Malaysia, granting the right Seniors from Japan can enter the country without a visa in order to Stimulating time Of this group of tourists who will Leading to economic development and growth Of the next country. [3]

The tourism industry is an industry with high growth. And generate income into Thailand as A large amount of such growth has affected the country's economic and social system as Thailand has Beautiful natural resources Has a cultural identity Traditions and way of life, including Have service potential Which is an opportunity to create tourism value It also affects growth. Of the labor market And distribution of prosperity to every region of the country [4] With And due to the social structure change with the increasing elderly people, the tourism industry Thai people have adapted to accommodate this change by targeting tourism target groups for Elderly tourists Which has a tourism model that focuses on creating quality experiences Profound Within tourist attractions Want to absorb, learn and create spiritual values for tourists Through activities Travel related to life, culture or nature [5] The elderly tourists are the most important tourist groups. One of the most important groups of the world Due to the increasing rate They are quick and have the power to spend on tourism. If considering the classification of tourists in groups The elderly, [6] provided information on the grouping of tourists. A variety of elderly groups such as [7] divided the elderly tourists into 3 groups according to the type of

travel.1) Groups that travel to visit relatives and acquaintances (Family Travelers) 2) Groups who like to plan their travel in advance. They like to do a variety of activities while traveling (Active Resters) and 3) groups that buy travel programs on a package basis [8] At present, Thailand has begun to focus on the elderly. Because in the future it is predicted that Thailand will have an aging population. The elderly in Thailand will account for 32.1% of the nation's population, or about 20.5 million people in the year 2040. It can be seen that the aging society has become closer to Thai people. Compared to traditional Japanese society, public buildings that are designed for the elderly are inevitable with hotels or accommodations for the elderly.

As a result, It is interested in doing research on the Tourism Activities for Elderly's in Thailand to be a guideline for the development of cooperation in the tourism industry for Thai elderly's Tourists in Thailand business operators and to build confidence in elderly's foreign tourists.

II. OBJECTIVES/RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The objectives of this research article were to study tourism activities for elderly's in Thailand

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The framework of this quantitative research is based on related concepts and theories to study the need for hotel elderly's in Thailand with details as follows.

Figure 1 Conceptual framework of this study

Research Methodology

Population and sample group

The population was Thai elderly's Tourists in Thailand. The sample group consisted of 400 respondents by non-probability sampling and accidental sampling. The number was obtained by calculating the formula without the population at a 95% confidence level, and the sample size was set as follows

$$n = \frac{Z^2 P(1-P)}{E^2}$$

Where:

n = Size of the sample group

Z = Reliability level

P = Proportion of the population

E = Highest error value which will happen

The acceptance level was in accordance with the statistical significance level at 0.5

$$n = \frac{(1.96)^2(0.5)(1-0.5)}{(0.05)^2}$$
$$= 384.16$$

The sample size was 385 respondents. However, 400 questionnaires were gathered by using a probabilistic sampling method between August - December 2020.

Research Instrument

The research tool was a questionnaire where the samples were asked individually to provide information about tourism activities for elderly's in Thailand. The content consisted of 3 parts as follows.

Part 1: General information of the respondents, namely gender, age, and average monthly income

Part 2: Information on factors used in the analysis of tourism activities for elderly's in Thailand

Part 3: Information on the concordance between the tourism activities and the set of results to Thai elderly's in Thailand.

Data analyses

The data were collected by distributing questionnaires in the form of filling in information online to provide convenience and speed to comply with the situation of the COVID-19 outbreak.

The quantitative data were analyzed with descriptive statistics for the concordance between the tourism activities and the set of results for elderly's in Thailand by analyzing the correlation coefficient and stepwise multiple regression.

IV. RESULTS

Regarding general data of the respondents, the following were found: For the general information of the respondents, it was found that 220 respondents, 60%, were female, and 180, 40%, were male. 187 respondents were between 60-65 years old, 43.50%. 137 of them were 66 - 70 years, 18.50%. There were 35 respondents aged 75-80 years, 17.50%, and were 28 respondents aged 81-85 years, 14%. For the age 85 and over, there were 13 respondents, 6.50%.

Most of the informants, For average monthly income, most of them had an average monthly income of 300,001 - 400,000 baht, 183, 41.50%. There were 40 respondents, 20%, who got 200,000 baht or more average monthly income. For 600,001 - 800,000 baht average monthly income, 128 respondents, 14%, were involved. There were 21 respondents, 10.5%, who got 500,000 - 600,001 baht average monthly income. For the respondents who got less than 700,000 baht average monthly income, it was 7, 3.5%.

The results of the analysis of tourism activities for elderly's in Thailand.

Tourism activities for elderly's in Thailand as a whole were for the whole of Tourism activities, activities (X_1) ($\beta = 0.512$, $\alpha < .01$) and time (X_4) ($\beta = 0.327$, $\alpha < .05$) had a statistically significant effect on the elderly's in Thailand. with a statistically significant effect, respectively. They could jointly describe the variance of Tourism activities for elderly's in Thailand by 61.2% ($R^2 = 0.612$) and the forecasting equations for Tourism activities affected the success of the Thai elderly's in Thailand. Among Thailand on the whole (Y) in standardized form was $Z_y = 0.512ZX_1 + 0.327ZX_4$ Results of analysis of Tourism activities for elderly's in Thailand.

Tourism activities for elderly's in Thailand terms of cost retardation, it was found that time (X_4) ($\beta = 0.327$, $\alpha < .05$) affected tourism activities for elderly's in Thailand with statistically significance. It could jointly explain the variance of tourism activities that affected for Thai elderly's in Thailand by 61.2% ($R^2 = 0.612$), and the equation for forecasting the need for hotel for elderly's in Thailand that affected the success of the need for hotel for elderly's in Thailand term of cost retardation (Y) in standardized form was $ZY = 0.512ZX_1 + 0.327ZX_4$.

V. DISCUSSIONS

The results revealed that overall tourism activities for elderly's in Thailand as a whole were of Tourism activities, activities (X_1) ($\beta = 0.512$, $\alpha < .01$) and time (X_4) ($\beta = 0.327$, $\alpha < .05$) had a statistically significant effect on the elderly's in Thailand. with a statistically significant effect, respectively. They could jointly describe the variance of Tourism activities for elderly's in Thailand by 61.2% ($R^2 = 0.612$) and the forecasting equations for Tourism activities affected the success of the Thai elderly's in Thailand. Among Thailand on the whole (Y) in standardized form was $Z_y = 0.512ZX_1 + 0.327ZX_4$ Results of analysis of Tourism activities for elderly's in Thailand. This was consistent with the concept of Elderly section [9] They spend their retirement years working

and engaging in various activities, especially recreational activities and Leisure travel Nature excursion Learn art, culture, history. This is in order to gain new experiences and spend a lot of time because they have more time than other travelers. This group of tourists focuses on good quality tourism and services, worthwhile, buying for reasons, not emotions, giving priority to satisfaction. Take a long break High spending Have the ability to purchase services at high prices Because it is ready Finance from the savings after retirement, while taking into account the confidence in safety. Service confidence, cares for good health, choose activities suitable for age and health. [10] According to the motivation and experience, the study and the elderly group aged 56-93 were found that It is the third most important number of people who focus on learning. Seek new experiences or experiences that have never been experienced before. Satisfied when you get more. Knowledge or have New activities They feel that they are still valued and have achieved their goals in life. Consistent with learning motivation The need to learn In what they are interested in seeking new things that have never been touched I have never seen this before and makes me feel that I still have value. [11] Tourism Business Development Model for the Elderly: Case Study Elderly in the central region " It consists of 8 components: (1) tourism operators play an important role in organizing (2) the tour guide's responsibility is to understand nature. And the psychology of the elderly (3) seeking the readiness of suitable tourist sites. The facilities Convenient for that tourist attraction (4) Good quality service is one of the contributing factors to satisfaction and Excellent service that meets the needs of the elderly (5) appropriate activities arrangement, organizing Activities that build relationships between each other (6) Entertainment for happiness is the creation of physical happiness. And the heart to enjoy And good for health (7) Pay attention to safety by providing The importance of transportation (8). Reliability in management. marketing. Services that meet the needs of the elderly, find flaws for improvement and Development of tourism for the elderly's.

III. CONCLUSION

Thailand is about to enter the second level, known as "Aged society" refers to a society or country with a population of more than 20% of the population aged 60 years or more, or with a population of 60 years or more than 14% of the entire population. In addition to the coronavirus problem In Thailand, we still need to follow up and solve daily problems. On the other hand, Thailand still has to prepare for the transition to in the next year, both the public and private sectors have to make a big adjustment. Especially in the tourism industry, which is the main backlash in generating Thai income, they must adjust quickly before anyone else. Even if it is an elderly person but it was found that this population tends to be more healthy as well as more wealthy. When entering the year 2020, the products and services that will be hot are inevitable. Business groups related to innovation for the elderly and services for the elderly which this group of people has tremendous purchasing power "Retire" tourists are willing to pay for what they think they can help stay healthy. And services That can make you happy in life after retirement Whether it is a vacation for the elderly As well as health products and supplements Including business in health and fitness.

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